

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 1; Issue 1; 2023; Page No. 304-308

Received: 07-08-2023

Accepted: 17-09-2023

Effectiveness of criminal law provisions in addressing gender-based violence

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214957>

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Abstract

The effectiveness of criminal law provisions in addressing gender-based violence (GBV) is a critical area of study and action, as GBV continues to pose significant challenges to gender equality and societal well-being. Over the years, legislative frameworks have been strengthened globally to criminalize various forms of violence, including domestic violence, sexual assault, trafficking, and honor-based crimes. These laws aim to protect victims, deter perpetrators, and ensure justice. However, their impact is often hindered by systemic barriers such as inadequate enforcement, societal stigma, and secondary victimization within the justice system. Research highlights that victim-sensitive approaches, survivor-centric judicial procedures, and multi-sectoral collaboration significantly enhance the effectiveness of these laws. Furthermore, coordinated efforts between law enforcement, healthcare, and community organizations can foster a more comprehensive response to GBV. While progressive legal frameworks exist, their success depends on addressing implementation gaps, increasing awareness, and fostering societal attitudes that reject violence in all its forms. This study underscores the need for holistic strategies to ensure that criminal law provisions are not only robust but also effectively implemented to protect survivors and reduce the prevalence of GBV.

Keywords: Criminal, fostering, violence, sexual, victimization, survivor

Introduction

Globally, one-third of women will be victims of gender-based violence at some point in their lives. More and more, the whole community is realizing that ending this kind of brutality must be a top priority. "Eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres." That is the precise wording used to describe one of the Sustainable Development Goals. While there is hope for increased government commitment because to increasing worldwide awareness of the issue, finding a solution will not be a picnic, according to a recent special series in *The Lancet* that focuses on ending violence against women.

Violence against women is a crime, and laws that make it a crime also guarantee women the right to be safe from violence. By making it clear that this kind of conduct is not acceptable in society, laws may serve as powerful symbols. Sanctions that are linked to this might act as a deterrent. It is possible that both levers will be effective in reducing violence in the real world. We have indirect data on both

fronts, but it is difficult to notice which is more successful. Legislation may also show empathy by addressing victims' needs for safety nets and assistance.

Results from the inquiry provide insight into more general discussions about the merits of human rights legislation on a global scale. While some see international treaties and accords as meaningless formalities, proponents of their use argue that they have really served to galvanize women's movements. Potentially influencing one pathway is the following. Domestic policy making is influenced by international laws and norms in multiple ways. First, domestic legislation is shaped by these norms. Second, global civil society is able to advocate and monitor these norms. Lastly, domestic civil society is mobilized around these new shared expectations of individual and state behavior.

The possibilities and limitations of legislative action are explored in this study, along with the manner in which national and international laws might interact with norms to reduce the likelihood of violence. We contend that, because

to the efforts of civil society groups on a global and national scale, women have made tremendous strides in securing protections against violence in both domestic and international law, particularly in the last ten years or more. Simultaneously, there is still a long way to go before we can break the cycle of violence and its accompanying behaviors and customs.

Gender-based violence, inequality and discrimination

To define "violence that is directed against a woman because she is a woman or that affects women disproportionately," the phrase Gender Based Violence (GBV) was first coined to characterize the overlaps between acts of violence against women and discrimination based on gender. The term "gender-based violence" (GBV) has evolved to encompass acts of aggression that cause or are likely to cause bodily, sexual, or psychological harm or suffering to an individual because of their gender, whether because of discrimination, stereotypes, or the unequal power dynamics associated with gender.

The state must act to eradicate systemic and pervasive forms of discrimination that give rise to gender-based violence. Gender-based violence (GBV) has its origins in traditional ideas of masculinity, which include the urge to exert dominance, define and enforce responsibilities, and discourage or penalize actions seen as contrary to these standards. Sexual violence against women is seen as both a fundamental human right and an extreme kind of discrimination that falls within the purview of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW). It hinders or eliminates the ability to exercise other basic freedoms and human rights, such as the right to personal security, the right to equal protection under the law, and the right to be free from torture and other cruel, dehumanizing, or humiliating treatment or punishment.

The global community, and especially international organizations, have come a long way in elucidating the many manifestations of gender-based violence (GBV), its root causes, the characteristics that put persons at risk, and the duties of governments in this area. A major shift in the field's perspective has been the worldwide community's rising awareness of GBV as distinct from other types of interpersonal violence due to its origins in and maintenance of prejudice. Victims of gender-based violence (GBV) may be individuals or groups, and their gender is a key factor in the power imbalances that give rise to the problem.

Because they are women and girls, GBV disproportionately impacts women in the community. This has linkages to discrimination and bias, damaging gender stereotypes, gender-based power disparities, and societal gender inequality. However, GBV is also used to degrade, humiliate, and dominate men and boys in some highly masculinized situations, such places of deprivation of liberty. In communities where people are deprived of their freedom, men who are seen as not fitting the societal norms of masculinity owing to their real or imagined sexual orientation or identity may also be victims of gender-based violence. Detainees who identify as transgender or intersex may also face discrimination since they do not fit the stereotypical gender norms. Because it may hinder victims from seeking protection or justice for human rights

breaches, inequality is both a cause and an effect of GBV. Therefore, it is essential to prevent GBV by promoting gender equality and safeguarding human rights in locations of deprivation of liberty.

Limitations of the laws

During India's colonial era, laws were enacted to safeguard women and girls from abuse and violence. For this reason, many statutes and sections thereof were passed to accomplish this goal; they include, but are not limited to, the Indian Evidence Act of 1872, the Code of Criminal Procedure Code of 1973, and the Indian Penal Code of 1860. But they weren't enough to stop the increasing number of crimes committed against women and girls, therefore they were discarded after a while.

In response to the tragic Nirbhaya rape case in December 2012, lawmakers passed the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013 to address these issues. Crucially, the Act aims to establish, among other things, a severe punishment of at least 20 years in prison or the death penalty in cases where the victim is dead or left in a "vegetative state" for those who commit heinous acts of rape or gang rape. For the first time, it included provisions in the Indian Penal Code that dealt with crimes including human trafficking, acid assaults, touching, stalking, and voyeurism. In addition to a fee that may cover the victim's medical expenses in the event of an acid assault, the penalty is a 10-year prison sentence.

It is reasonable to say that the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013, has a few positive aspects, according to Amnesty International Chief Executive Ananth Guruswamy. The fact that it addresses the needs of those with physical disabilities and criminalizes violence against women is praiseworthy. Additionally, it removes a legal hurdle for the prosecution of public officials suspected of GBV offenses and establishes victim-friendly processes for the examination of evidence. Having said that, I concur with Ananth Guruswamy in his assessment that the legislation is inadequate in its coverage of gender-based violence (GBV) against women and girls, notwithstanding these successes. This essay will answer four concerns that have been raised: ambiguity, prejudice, breadth, and incomprehensibility of the legislation; inconsistency with international standards.

The law's lack of clarity

According to Begum, the definition of terms like "insult" and "outrage to women's modesty" under sections 354 and 509 of the IPC is left vague in the code and the Criminal Law Act does not deal with this problem. This is so because the language perpetuates a harmful stereotype about battered women and their mental and physical health. In addition, Burgess and Holmstrom make a reasonable case that this idea elevates women to more of a status symbol, which diminishes the penal responsibility of crimes perpetrated against them. The sexual objectification of "victims" may lead to less rapist responsibility, if this is really the case. According to Burgess and Holmstrom, women should dress modestly to protect their own dignity and the honor of their families; if they do otherwise, they bring disgrace upon themselves and their community. Because these ideas are not defined by law, "negative reactions and stereotypic judgment about victims of sexual violence" might flourish. As a result, victims experience psychological

dehumanization and fear social estrangement, making the process of coming to court an even more crisis than the attack or rape itself.

Furthermore, Bhattacharyya notes that while it is commendable that new sections of the Indian Penal Code have been added, such as S.354C on Voyeurism, S. 354D on stalking, S.370A on Employing a trafficked person, and S.326A on acid attacks, among other things, "it remains unclear as to how the perpetrators of the offences like touching, stalking, and sexually colored remarks would be accused and subsequently prove the assailant guilty." To sidestep this problem, the legal system places the onus of evidence on the accused. Since this goes against the basic principle of innocence until proved guilty, it further creates paradox. Unnecessary shame, anguish, and suffering has befallen men and their families as a consequence of fraudulent complaints being filed, undoubtedly. As previously stated, there has been a very low rate of conviction for voyeurism, stalking, and insults to women's modesty, even though the number of reported incidents of these offenses increased to 84,746 in 2016 according to NCRB. It seems that there are problematic methods for collecting evidence necessary to prosecute these crimes. On the other side, Satish and Majumder make the arguable point that a lack of evidence might lead to the conviction of innocent persons in some instances. However, this provision of the statute hinders the expeditious charging and prosecution of criminals.

under addition, Halder concedes that the language used to define internet voyeurism and "bad talk" under the IT Act is inadequate. The police are able to use their judgment in deciding what qualifies as "annoying speech," and its ambiguity leaves space for abuse by those who want to victimize others. It should be mentioned that the anonymity of the internet gives abusers a lot of leeway. The Uttar Pradesh police have been unable to capture or punish those who sell rape videos on the street, according to Halder's argument, due to the lack of clarity. It allows for erroneous and subjective interpretation, which further undermines the clarity of the legal principles. The 2012 Supreme Court ruling in *Shreya Singhal v. Union of India* no.167 made this point very plain. Due to its vagueness and its restriction of free expression in cyberspace, the section of the act pertaining to voyeurism was deemed unconstitutional, and the accused was subsequently acquitted.

Gender based violence in India: Seethal Ranjan's 2013 research on female victims of crime in India included a wide spectrum of offenses. National Crime Records Bureau numbers are also analyzed in the research. The study's inclusion of a wider variety of gender-based crimes makes it inconclusive. This is due to the fact that, following 2013 in India, the special report of the Justice Verma Committee suggested a number of changes to the definitions and laws pertaining to gender-based crimes. Since then, the number of categories on offenses against women has expanded dramatically in the Crime in India portion of the National Crime Records Bureau Report, Crime against Women.

Using the same methods, Mukherjee, Rustagi, and Krishnaji (2001) also used NCRB information on crime in India. Regional trends in crimes perpetrated against women in India were examined experimentally in this research.

Serious crimes, such as sexual assaults and rapes, are more common in central district areas of India, specifically in different portions of Madhya Pradesh, according to the authors. Investigating the relationship between reported crime occurrences and socio-economic parameters such as sex ratio, female literacy rate, and employment was also done by Mukherjee, Rustagi, and Krishnaji (2001). Although they did find a correlation between dowry-related murders and the sex ratio, they did not find a correlation between the literacy rate of women and the overall crime rate. Another group that has contended that rape, molestation, and sexual harassment are more common among women who work is Mukherjee, Rustagi, and Krishnaji (2001). Due to changes in the NCRB data throughout time, it is predicted that the conclusions or interpretation of the research will be different in this study.

According to research by Mangoli and Tarase (2009), which looked at data from 2003–2007 and the percentage change from 2006–2007, the rate of crime against women rose dramatically, going from 7.6% to 8.8% in that time. The study is limited by being obsolete and does not include the full categories of crime against women that the NCRB report currently covers, much as earlier studies.

Also looking at how big of an issue violence against women is on a worldwide basis is Charlotte Watts and Cathy Zimmerman (2002). They said that worldwide, violence against women has been on the rise. The writers mostly concentrated on the most prevalent and severe types of violence against women, such as domestic abuse, human trafficking, female infanticide, and exploitation for work or prostitution. Additional types of violence against women, including as acid assaults, female genital mutilation, dowry-related fatalities, and so on, have been brought up by Watts and Zimmerman (2002). Another reason to do more research on gender-based violence, similar to what Charlotte and Zimmerman did years ago, is that this warrants it.

Lack of victim-sensitive approaches in court procedures

The way victims are handled by the criminal justice system is a major factor in case attrition. In addition to a culture of impunity, women who have been victims of violence do not have faith in the criminal justice system because of persistent evidence of secondary victimization by the system. The very nature of going to court makes victims wary of coming forward to the authorities, according to one poll. The criminal justice system contributes to re-traumatization. Due to the widespread dismissal, minimization, or blaming of the victims by law enforcement, prosecutors, and judges, many women see the reaction of the criminal justice system as akin to a "second assault". Being a crucial witness in the trial of your claimed rapist is no different from being a victim of sexual assault, with the exception that the latter occurred in front of an audience. Some victims have gone so far as to say that this "second rape" is even worse. According to research, the complainant feels that they are the ones on trial, and they have even said things like being unable to tell the difference between the attorneys representing the prosecution and the defense. The prosecution failed to safeguard the victims' character, they were seldom given an opportunity to tell their tale, and the defense often failed to refute evidence that disproved their claims.

Important choices are seldom made with the victims' input. Although there are laws and rules in place to ensure that people will be kept informed, research reveals that this is not always the case. As a result, individuals have false expectations about the criminal justice system and are left in the dark about what to anticipate. Courtroom strategies that prioritize victims' needs are just as crucial as the case's final verdict. Victims felt more empowered and safer after their court experiences, according to some. None of the victims regretted taking their case to trial, even if they were let down by the verdict, since they were encouraged, educated, and involved at every stage. According to another research, victims' satisfaction is closely related to the level of empathy and compassion shown by court personnel.

A whole-of-government approach is essential for an adequate response to GBV: In order to strategically prioritize policy requirements and obstacles in government action, it is crucial for the government to have a clear vision of its aims to combat GBV. Governments may outline their action scope in terms of the forms and kinds of GBV to be addressed, the range of solutions to be considered, and the stakeholders to be included with the help of this strategic framework. In order to create these frameworks, countries might adopt many techniques. For example, in 2022, the federal, provincial, and territorial governments of Canada endorsed a ten-year "National Action Plan to End Gender-Based Violence" that had been developed in collaboration with other organizations (Government of Canada, 2022) to combat GBV. The majority of responding nations, which included 21 OECD members, also prioritized addressing gender-based violence (GBV) as part of their overall national gender plans (OECD, 2021). The OECD Development Assistance Committee (DAC) has similarly established frameworks for the elimination of SEAH in the settings of development assistance and humanitarian relief, and its member nations have often implemented whole-of-government strategies in this regard.

Adopting a holistic approach to deal with GBV against women and girls: At the individual, interpersonal, communal, and societal levels, there are a number of interrelated variables that contribute to GBV (OECD, 2021). Thus, it is crucial that all societal and governmental levels work together to combat GBV with concrete measures and goals that will yield tangible results. At every level of combating GBV, nations may use this method to take measured, evidence-based actions.

To take a more comprehensive view, we must also acknowledge the many different experiences, perspectives, and histories that women and girls bring to the table. This shows that different groups of women in every community have varied risks of experiencing GBV. When formulating measures to combat gender-based violence, some OECD nations have used an intersectional approach.

Co-ordinated government action is needed for GBV prevention and response: Addressing GBV, a multi-sectoral problem, calls for concerted government effort involving many different parties. such as development agencies, independent monitoring organizations, parliaments, and judicial institutions at the federal level.

Developing and implementing strategies, policies, and activities pertaining to gender-based violence (GBV) falls on the shoulders of many OECD nations' central/national gender equality institutes (CGI).

The success of any whole-of-government initiative depends on appropriate procedures for coordination and support from across government agencies. A number of OECD nations have taken steps to combat gender-based violence (GBV), including Finland, Norway, and Spain, by forming official alliances or coordinating organizations among important state players. For instance, in Finland, the Ombudsman for Equality, Statistics Finland, and the Ministry of Justice are all part of the Committee for Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (NAPE), which is in charge of coordinating, monitoring, and impact assessing the measures needed to implement the Istanbul Convention. Legislative bodies and government agencies at the subnational level act as intermediaries between the national and central authorities. According to the OECD (2023), in the majority of nations, they are even more crucial in combating GBV. Given their close proximity to local communities, local governments may play a pivotal role in dispersing funding, creating capacity, and mobilizing communities, among other delegated tasks under the national GBV plan. For this reason, it is critical for the government's response to GBV to be coordinated at all levels, from the local to the national. To ensure comprehensive service provision for SEAH victim/survivors and GBV more broadly, it is critical for actors in development and humanitarian contexts to coordinate, including OECD Members, international organizations, civil society organizations, and local government authorities (when appropriate and safe).

By reviewing both current and prospective legislation, parliaments and parliamentary committees may improve the legal framework for responding to GBV. They may also keep an eye on how the government is carrying out its plans, programs, and laws. To guarantee that the state's reaction to GBV occurrences is survivor- and victim-centered, justice institutions, including national justice ministries, courts, and judges, play a crucial role. The police, as first responders, are often the victims' and survivors' first point of contact within the system; they may aid in the investigative process by reporting and conducting investigations in a gender-sensitive way. The steps taken in reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic show how important it is for government GBV prevention systems, institutions, and policies to be ready for unexpected and crisis-like scenarios. Australia, Canada, Iceland, Italy, and Sweden are just a few of the OECD countries that took action in response to the growing threat of gender-based violence (GBV) during the pandemic. Other countries, such as Iceland, Italy, and Sweden, implemented more targeted responses, such as emergency funding to ensure that survivors' services could be maintained and adjusted. Chile and Spain have taken measures to prevent gender-based violence. To avoid, control, and lessen the impact of GBV while incarcerated, for instance, the Spanish government laid up plans and procedures (Government of Spain, 2018; 2020). Additional actions taken by several nations included gathering data, forming special taskforces, and stepping up cooperation between governments (OECD, 2020; 2021). In response to

GBV, other nations' judiciaries have become more robust by imposing harsher criminal penalties (OECD, 2022).

Conclusion

The effectiveness of criminal law provisions in addressing gender-based violence lies in their ability to provide justice, deter offenders, and protect survivors. Over the years, legislative reforms have strengthened legal frameworks, such as criminalizing domestic violence, sexual harassment, and marital rape in various jurisdictions. While these laws signify progress, their practical implementation often encounters systemic barriers, including inadequate law enforcement training, victim-blaming attitudes, and a lack of survivor-centered support systems. Moreover, specialized mechanisms such as fast-track courts, victim compensation schemes, and protection orders have proven to enhance accessibility and efficiency in delivering justice. To truly address gender-based violence, criminal law provisions must be integrated with preventive measures, survivor rehabilitation, and a broader societal shift toward gender equality. This comprehensive approach ensures that the justice system not only punishes perpetrators but also fosters an environment where survivors feel empowered to seek justice and violence against women is effectively deterred.

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